

ATTRIBUTIVE PHRASES IN TRADITIONAL AND COGNITIVE ASPECTS OF LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Mukhamedova Lola Djurayevna

Doctor of Philosophy in Philology (PhD), docent

Department of Languages,
The Academy of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan
devostok@mail.ru

Annotation: *Modern people cannot imagine a world without the use of language. "We pass absolutely all the knowledge that we receive through the network of language," and then we transmit it to each other "as a result of subject-specific practical activity". Moreover, literally every time, uttering this or that word, phrase or sentence, a person, as if from a blank slate, is engaged in the generation of meanings, choosing the means of their representation. One of the means of representing generated meanings about any object of reality at the language level is an attributive phrase.*

Key words: *cognitive, aspect, study, meaning, discourse, classification, traditional, linguistics.*

INGLIZ TILINI O'RGANISHNING AN'ANAVIY VA KOGNITIV ASSPEKTIDAGI ATRIBUTIV FRAZALARI

Annotatsiya: *Zamonaviy odamlar dunyoni tildan foydalanmasdan tasavvur qila olmaydi. "Biz olgan barcha bilimlarimizni til tarmog'i orqali o'tkazamiz", so'ngra ularni "ma'lum bir mavzu bo'yicha amaliy faoliyat natijasida" bir-birimizga uzatamiz (o'sha erda). Bundan tashqari, tom ma'noda har safar u yoki bu so'z, ibora yoki jumlani talaffuz qilganda, odam xuddi bo'sh varaqdan chiqqandek, ma'nolarni yaratish, ularni ifodalash vositalarini tanlash bilan shug'ullanadi. Har qanday voqelik ob'ekti haqida hosil bo'lgan ma'nolarni til darajasida ifodalash vositalaridan biri atributiv iboradir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kognitiv, aspekt, o'rganish, ma'no, nutq, tasnif, an'anaviy, tilshunoslik.*

АТРИБУТИВНЫЕ ФРАЗЫ В ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ И КОГНИТИВНЫХ АСПЕКТАХ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация: Современные люди не могут представить мир без использования языка. «Абсолютно все знания, которые мы получаем, мы передаем через сеть языка», а затем передаем их друг другу «в результате предметно-практической деятельности» [Там же]. Более того, буквально каждый раз, произнося то или иное слово, фразу или предложение, человек как бы с чистого листа занимается порождением смыслов, выбором средств их репрезентации. Одним из средств представления сформированных значений о любом объекте действительности на языковом уровне является атрибутивная фраза.

Ключевые слова: когнитивный, аспект, исследование, значение, дискурс, классификация, традиционное, лингвистика.

The purpose of this work is to study the essence of the concept of “attributive phrase” from traditional and cognitive points of view with an attempt to determine its meaning for modern linguistics using the material of the English language.

The cognitive approach to the study of attributive phrases makes it possible to look at attributive constructions already known in traditional linguistics from the point of view of their modeling and organization at the mental level in the form of knowledge formats, which indicates the scientific novelty of the research being carried out. From these positions, it is logical to consider attributive phrases as an object of research and analyze the possibilities of formatting the knowledge behind these linguistic units using the material of the English language. Thus, in the light of the new paradigm that cognitive linguistics offers today, the issue raised in this article about a new understanding of the functioning of attributive phrases in language and in speech can be considered relevant.

The results of the study are theoretically valuable, since they contribute to the development of the theory of attributive phrases. In addition, they have practical significance and can be used in the development of lecture courses on vocabulary and grammar of the English language. Scientists from different years and even centuries have been studying attributive phrases.

Ideas about simple attributive judgments, in which something must belong to something, go back to Aristotle’s doctrine of logic. A logical pattern works in a simple judgment: a given thing (event or subject referred to in the judgment) may have a given attribute (understood by Aristotle as properties or states) potentially or actually.

If the semantic core of any object consists of its characteristic features, then the process of nominating it will look like an act of assigning to it such qualities and properties that would help to distinguish it from a number of similar objects and point to it without the need to constantly refer to the real-life thing behind it. by this name. Thus, in the Indo-European and Arabic linguistic traditions, a single category of ancient name existed for a long time. This was facilitated by the then current method of identifying ancient parts of speech, based on the morphological analysis of words and phrases.

“The traditional scheme of parts of speech survived until the 16th-17th centuries, after which it underwent some modifications.” By this time, it was established that the morphological and semantic properties of nominal parts of speech are different, from which arises the need to differentiate them: if nouns (being things or substances) exist on their own, then adjectives (being accidents or attributes) can only exist through nouns (substances). Thus, the initial indivisibility of the ancient name was subjected to classification, which resulted in the appearance of nominal parts of speech.

The concept of “attribute” goes back to the Latin *attributum* - attributed, given. O. S. Akhmanova defines this phenomenon as “the same as a definition,” and the word “attributive” is “relating to a definition, acting in the function of a definition, possessing the properties of a definition.” A. A. Shakhmatov proposes to consider an attribute as part of “what is common with the subject or object of perception that it defines,” therefore attributive relations should be understood as “properties between representations that are part of one complex, undivided representation.” Thus, the philosophical definition of the quality of a thing in the form of a set of properties indicating its “functional purpose both in interaction with other things and with the cognizing subject” corresponds to the grammatical category of attribute.

Thanks to the emerging relationships between words belonging to different parts of speech, connections arise at the morphological, lexical-semantic and syntactic levels, which leads to the formation of various kinds of phrases. Interest in this grammatical category has been observed since the 17th century. B. Johnson in his “Grammar,” without using the term “word combination,” made the assumption that within the framework of a combination of words, specific grammatical relations appear. One century later, J. Brightland, studying the phrase, noted that in grammatical relationships there must be a syntactic connection between words. Similar to Russian linguists of the 19th and early 20th centuries. L. Bloomfield understands a phrase as a syntactically organized group of words. Note that L. Bloomfield’s theory was significantly expanded in subsequent years, and in general there were other theories that offered their own interpretations of the essence of the phrase, for example, the

works of J. Ries, E. Kreising or O. Jespersen. Thus, considering phrases, researchers identified the difference between a phrase and a sentence, a phrase and a word, and came to the conclusion that a phrase is a special structural unit of language that has components inherent in both the word and the sentence.

In the middle of the 20th century, F. F. Fortunatov introduced the concept of “phrase,” which can be “finished” or “unfinished” depending on whether it is a building material for a sentence or indicates any object of reality. Am. speeches in immediate proximity form a phrase, but only those that are combined in thought... In order for two words to form a phrase, they must be combined simultaneously both in speech and in thought. A phrase as a word is an external-internal, physical-psychological unity.”

V.V. Vinogradov, on whose work many language researchers later relied, made a significant contribution to the development of the doctrine of word combination. He defined a phrase as “a product of the semantic distribution of a word,” which, like a word, is the basis used in the process of linguistic communication, and, like a sentence, tends to realize multiple meanings. However, in the theory proposed by the author, the phrase and the sentence are distinguished due to the fact that these are “concepts of different semantic series and different stylistic planes. They correspond to different forms of thinking. A sentence is not at all a type of phrase, since there are words of a sentence. But even in its inner essence, in terms of its constructive features, it cannot be directly derived from the phrase.”

By the end of the 60s of the 20th century, a generally accepted concept of the phrase and its types had developed in Russian linguistics, in which it was established that the phrase is a unit of syntax and has a certain structure. And, since the phrase exists semantically holistically, it represents a single semantic content necessary to designate an object, action or quality.

So, phrases began to be studied in more detail, received their description, a place in the system of language grammar and the possibility of identifying functionally different subclasses, one of which are attributive phrases (along with verbal, adverbial, objective and subjective phrases). Thus, the history of the study of attributive constructions turned out to be closely connected with the emergence and formation of such a syntactic unit as a phrase.

At this stage of the study, it seems natural to try to give our own definition of the attributive phrase. In order to formulate it, it is necessary to find out the main characteristics of the type of phrases under consideration, which are distinctive markers for the syntactic category under study.

There are many classifications of attributive phrases by various authors. For example, V.D. Arakin, in works devoted to the comparative typological analysis of the

English and Russian languages, describes an attributive phrase as a combination of two or more words agreed in gender, number, case and determinativity, which are characterized by the presence of both prepositive and and postpositive grammatical structures. In English, this is a certain two-term or three-term model, which is based on a nominative function that arose due to the syntactic connection “adjacent”, which is represented in a certain way in speech. From what we can conclude, that the classification of attributive phrases should be built on the basis of the following set of features: the nature of syntactic relations, the way of expressing syntactic relations and the position of the dependent word in relation to the main one.

According to another researcher V.V. Burlakova and her colleagues, the basis for the classification of any word combinations is the analysis of semantic relationships that arise between the elements of a noun phrase. She offers some of them for consideration using the example of the attribute construction Noun + Noun:

- 1) relationship between part and whole: the bathroom door (bathroom door);
- 2) location: the window seat;
- 3) the material from which the item is made: silver clock (silver watch);
- 4) temporal relations (temporal correlation): the Sunday evening (Sunday evening);
- 5) comparative relations: sapphire sky (sapphire sky);
- 6) purpose: the waste-paper basket (paper basket);
- 7) characteristic: pine forest (pine forest);
- 8) accessory: falcon eye (hawk eye);
- 9) source: radio noise.

There are other, no less interesting and original approaches to the classification of attributive phrases. These include the studies of V. Ya. Plotkin, who defines the phrase itself through the concept of “syntagma”. The classification capabilities of attributive phrases are based on the connection between the elements of the phrase, called adjacency, the distinctive feature of which is the maximum positional convergence in the process of semantic and grammatical association of the adjoining and leading words. Against the background of the presented type of connection, the author identifies two important parameters for the classification of attributive phrases:

- 1) Definition of preposition or postposition in a phrase;
- 2) Identification of the force of adjunction, which “manifests itself in a group of words - a subordinating syntagma, around the top of which - its leading member - the adjuncts inherent in it are located in accordance with the force of adjunct inherent in each adjunct.”

The author reinforces this classification with an example of parsing the sentence: “Happy little children sing songs merrily” (“happy little children sing songs merrily”), in which one of the phrase groups selected for classification is the nominal syntagma “happy little children”. In the analyzed phrase, the vertex “children” stands out, which “attracts” the adjuncts “happy” and “little” to itself. As the researcher notes, “the definition with the meaning of the more stable age characteristic “little” is more closely related than the definition of the variable characteristic of the emotional state “happy,” which makes it impossible to use these definitions in a different sequence in English.”

The problem of classification of attributive phrases was illuminated most thoroughly by N. A. Kobrina and her colleagues. In the work devoted to the syntax of the English language, two parts can be distinguished: the definition of the concept of “attribute” and the methods of its expression. The author considers an attribute as a minor member of a sentence that can characterize a person or object, adding semantic load to the main word in a phrase through quality, quantity or description of a situation. In this case, the emphasis is placed on the fact that the attribute can become an element of only a noun phrase. In this study, the classification of attributive structures is multifaceted, since it includes the following parameters:

1) Ways of expressing attributive phrases, which include various combinations of nominal parts of speech, morphological means of combining words into attributive constructions, the possibility of transitioning the semantic role from an object to an attribute, special techniques for changing the forms and sizes of phrases using gerunds, infinitives, adverbs, adverbs phrases and whole sentences;

2) Positional changes in the position of attributes in a phrase, when the speaker has the opportunity to place a dependent word before or after the word being defined;

3) Analysis of the types of connections between attributes and main words, which includes inseparable attributes with the “adjacent” connection, as well as attributes separated by commas.

These parameters help to cope with the understanding of the subject and object of study at the linguistic level, however, since the 60s of the 20th centuries. The linguistic science has not stopped developing, and therefore today it allows us to look at attributive phrases from other positions, taking into account extralinguistic factors that influence significant influence on understanding the place and role of attributive phrases in the system of any language, in particular English.

An attributive phrase is similar to a word, since it is also capable of reflecting a certain fragment of reality and indicating it. It follows from this that the attributive phrase is one of the ways to nominate objects in the surrounding world. In addition, an attribute within the attribute structure is “a means of summarizing information and

isolating significant qualities (properties) of the defined concept, i.e. a specific object as a fragment of reality." This understanding of the structure under study makes it possible to call it a unit of a complex nomination.

In the second half of the 20th century, as an alternative to traditional research in the field of linguistics and linguistics, a new branch of language research began to actively develop, called cognitive linguistics, the focus of which was the relationship between cognitive (cognitive) and linguistic structures. Cognitive linguistics "relies on the study of the conceptual and empirical (based on human experience) basis of linguistic categories and concepts.

In addition, the format of knowledge presupposes the presence of a certain structural organization, that is, its own content and structural typology. It follows that any linguistic category can be considered as a conceptual structure that combines knowledge of the objects themselves and knowledge of the principles and mechanisms of their association. Modern English literature, in all its diversity of genres, has its own style characteristics, manifested in the conciseness of presentation and the density of information. Attributive phrases make it possible to achieve this goal, since they are a way to make speech concise and more concentrated, thanks to which their study has not lost its significance for many years. The main task of attributive constructions is to form in the reader a certain assessment of ongoing events through the display of signs, properties or qualities inherent in the described object of reality. L.N. Shelontseva drew attention to the use of attributive phrases in A. Murdoch's novel "The Sea, the Sea". In particular, A. Murdoch, describing the interior of the house, draws the reader's attention to the vase: "a large remarkably hideous green vase" ("a large, surprisingly disgusting green vase"). The phrase reveals the dominant sense of the negative quality of the object, its external disharmony.

Examples show that attributive phrases help in the development of the narrative, since at the semantic level they perform nominative, communicative and expressive functions, participating in the processes of nomination of the surrounding space and entering into theme-rhematic relations at the text level. "Identification of an object is achieved through the interaction of a number of word combinations, each of which characterizes the object from a new perspective, thereby expanding and complementing the existing information" about it.

For adequate production, perception and interpretation of attributive phrases, the car and the reader turn to formatting knowledge about these nominative units, which means taking into account the nature and categories of such constructions and, in particular, the semantic connections within the attributive phrase. In addition, "in the course of interpretation, a person can represent the world in language through certain

linguistic units, depending on the nature of the projection of the individual conceptual system onto the existing collective knowledge, which is the result of concepts and models of conceptualization and categorization created within the framework of previous types of cognitive activity of people.”

On this basis, a systematic description of the totality of categorical knowledge behind attributive phrases in the English language as a special format of knowledge, as well as the identification of the interpretive capabilities of this format during its implementation in oral or written speech, seems promising. Summarizing the study, it is worth noting that the attributive phrase has received a large number of definitions during its existence. From the standpoint of traditional linguistics, an attributive phrase is understood by researchers as a kind of verbal construction consisting of a defined component and words defining it. At the same time, representatives of cognitive linguistics consider the attributive phrase as a unit of complex nomination, which at the mental and linguistic levels reflects and points to a certain fragment of reality.

Thus, this article, using methods of linguistic observation and generalization, made it possible to present an overview of the results of theoretical works devoted to the issues of attributive constructions, and to give our own definition of an attributive phrase based on the study of the features inherent in these linguistic units.

As the analysis of linguistic material has shown, the role of attributive phrases in English artistic discourse is quite important, since this type of phrases takes an active part in the processes of nominating objects in the surrounding world. Each attributive phrase introduced into a literary text complement and details the existing information about a particular object of reality, forming in readers the attitude towards any character, object or event necessary for the author. Such an artistic effect becomes achievable thanks to the flexibility of human thinking, which lies in the free formatting of the knowledge behind attributive constructions.

List of sources:

1. Abramova I. Yu. Nature and functions of attributive phrases (based on the material of the Russian Slavic Prologue of the 16th century) // Bulletin of the Nizhny Novgorod University. N.I. Lobachevsky. 2013. No. 6-2. Pp. 17-20.
2. Alpatov V. M. History of linguistic teachings: textbook. Allowance. 4th edition, rev. And additional M.: Languages of Slavic Culture, 2005. 368 p.
3. Arakin V.D. Comparative typology of English and Russian languages: textbook. Allowance. 3rd edition. M.: FIZMATLIT, 2005. 232 p.
4. Akhmanova O. S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. M.: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1966. 608 p.
5. Мухамедова, Л. Д. Эффективность социальных сетей в изучение языка / Л. Д. Мухамедова // novainfo.Ru. – 2019. – № 109. – С. 74-75. – EDN XRKDVJ.
6. Мухамедова, Л. Д. ЗАИМСТВОВАННЫЙ ТЕРМИН КАК ЕДИНИЦА ТЕРМИН СИСТЕМЫ (Теоретические исследования в области терминологии). ХОРИЙИ ТИЛЛАРИ О‘ҚИТИШНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ МАСАЛАЛАРИ: МУАММОЛАР ВА ЙЕЧИМЛАР, 110.
7. Akhmanova O. S. Dictionary of linguistic terms. M.: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1966. 608 p.
8. Мухамедова, Л. Д. (2019). Управление самостоятельной учебной деятельностью курсантов в процессе обучения иностранному языку в военном вузе. Integration of information technologies and foreign languages in globalization, 407 pp.